

THE PROPOSITION ANALYSIS OF THE SERIES OF THE JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEXT-BOOKS

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ABSTRACT

It is proposition density, an important factor in texts, that plays a crucial role in text comprehension and retention. The combination of text comprehension and retention suggests that proposition density can be useful in the selection of textbooks. The criteria of compiling textbooks must have the evaluation of proposition density based on the meanings of the sentences. Currently, it is difficult to find any published studies relating to proposition density used as evaluation criteria of textbooks in Vietnam, especially textbooks on foreign languages. Therefore, the author believes that the results of this study will contribute new information to the database for compiling textbooks and the subsequent works. The research analyses, identifies and compares the proposition density through the number of meanings of sentences to show a logical evaluation in four pilot textbooks and propose directions for the compilation of textbooks in the future.

Key words: Comprehension, meaning, proposition density, retention, textbook

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview of the research situation

Nowadays, in developed countries, linguists begin to apply the developmental aspects of linguistics to setting new criteria for compiling textbooks. According to the development of linguistics, discourse analysis has been increasingly perfected with new theories and applied to teaching and learning. The meaning of the sentence is constructed and developed into propositions, which forms the scientific basis for defining sentences with few propositions (simple sentences) or sentences with high proposition density (Complex sentences). In this study, we use the proposition density as criteria for comparing sentence structures to arrange sentences on a gradual scale to help students logically learn lessons from one level to the next.

To help us comprehend the meaning of sentence structures in English textbooks 6, 7, 8 and 9 (published in 2015 by Nguyen Van Loi as the Chief Editor) [8], we conducted an analysis of the sentence patterns according to the modern propositional criteria which have been in use by scholars. However, up to now no scholar has summed up these criteria, although many have presented the analysis in almost the same way. We have done research on this issue and incorporated propositional patterns into formulas for the purpose of analyzing the meaning of

sentences, as the basis for scientifically evaluating the levels of language learning, namely in English 6, 7, 8 and 9.

Students at elementary level are not able to absorb sentences with dense propositions. This is beyond the capacity of the students and therefore they will understand vaguely and even understand nothing. For upper students, if the sentences are composed of very few propositions and the meanings are too simple, they are bored and do not feel interested in learning or reading. Selecting sentences with appropriate proposition density in accordance with the learner's ability is to help them maximize their learning and self-learning.

1.2 Literature review

In terms of the meaning of the text, proposition is an important concept for researchers. According to T. B. Jay [5], proposition is a unit of meaning, a statement expressing a practical requirement. W. Kintsch (1974) and Kintsch & Keenan (1973) [6,7] argue that proposition is a fundamental unit involved in the comprehension and archives of texts. "The propositions correspond to verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, and conjunctions (not nouns or pronouns)" (M.A. Covington, 2008, p. 2).

Researchers have made use of propositions to compare documents. According to them, otherwise it is impossible to make comparisons (David, N. 1989: 55 [4]). Texts with similar contents and grammatical structures are difficult for us to decide which are easier to read and to remember. The propositions of the sentences are the decisive factor of the complex characteristics of the texts. Kintsch and Keenan (1973) [7] conducted the experiments and concluded that the students comprehend and remember the texts with fewer propositions better than the more ones.

According to Atkinson & Shiffrin (1968) [1], for new language learners or students at a low basic level, the initial proposition density is the lowest and will increase gradually in a compatible manner. The proper adaptation of propositions will help learners acquire and remember the amount of information.

Charmaine DeFrancesco & Kyle Perkins [3] said that we can divide the information into smaller parts to help students grasp the ideas. This is an effective way to help students understand and apply small amounts of information easily when their background knowledge is low.

So far, foreign authors have put forward rules for propositional phrasing in sentences, but these rules are fragmentary, incomplete and not universal for later research. Based on the types of simple, compound and complex sentences, we propose a set of rules for analyzing propositions in sentences, firstly in English ones.

1.3 Objective

The authors will review the books in a scientific way based on the research and inductive propositional rules to analyze the logic of the books: Raising the strong points of the books and mapping out the weak points of the books. This is a positive contribution to the compilation of the future books edited and compiled by the Ministry of Education and Training.

1.4 Methodology

The research was conducted with the following methods:

The research was conducted with inductive method: theoretical research on gathering the rules of propositional analysis in discourse. This is the basis of the theory that underlies the research. We set the criteria for analyzing the books on semantics and syntactic structures.

The research is also conducted with the survey method: the survey of English books in grades 6-9 of the junior secondary program circulated from 2004 up to now. Finally, the research is conducted with comparison method in collecting and processing data: selecting sample sentences in the books to analyze and compare the clause density.

2 PROPOSITIONAL FORMULAS AND ANALYSIS

2.1 Formulas-criteria for propositional analysis

On the basis of the studies by foreign scholars, we incorporated the sentence patterns into 37 formulas-criteria to facilitate the analysis of propositional density in sentence patterns. Many scholars use normal letters to analyze propositions. We endorse the use of capital letters by David Nunan [4] when analyzing propositions in sentences.

1. S + V _i : (Intransitive) V _i , S	21. V + S ...?: (Yes-No questions) V + C/O, S
2. S + V _t : (monotransitive) V _t , S, O	22. WH + (Aux) + S + V?: (WH questions) Aux V, S, WH WH = (...)
3. S + V _t : (ditransitive) V _t , S, O _d (Prep) O _i	23. Intensifiers + S + V + O: (Sentence Intensifiers) V, S, O (V, S, O), Intensifiers
4. S + V _t + O + OC: (ditransitive) V _t , S, O, WHO/WHAT WHO/WHAT = ...	24. Intensifiers + S + V + O: (Word/phrase Intensifiers) V, S, O Word/phrase + Intensifiers
5. S + V _t + To V (Infinitive) V _t , S To V, (S), (O)	25. S + V + Modification + modification + N: (Repeated Modification) V, S
6. S + V _t + V-ING (Gerund) V _t , S, V-ING	

<p>7. S, V_t, V-ING + (O) (Gerund phrase)</p> <p>V_t + S + V-ING</p> <p>V-ING + O</p> <p>8. S + V_i + Prep V-ING (Gerund)</p> <p>V_t, S</p> <p>Prep V-ING</p> <p>9. S + V_i + Prep Phrase (Intransitive)</p> <p>V_i, S</p> <p>Prep Phrase</p> <p>10. S + V + NOT + (...) (Negative form)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>NEG n't</p> <p>11. S + V + Prep (...) N: (Noun Modification)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>Prep (...) N</p> <p>N, (...)</p> <p>12. S + V + Prep + clause + (...) N: (embedded clause)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>Prep (...) N</p> <p>N, (...)</p> <p>(...), Clause</p> <p>13. S + V + (...): (DirectQuote)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>(...), (S)</p> <p>14. S + V + ADV: (Verb modification)</p> <p>V, S</p>	<p>(Prep) N</p> <p>N, Modification</p> <p>Modification, Modification</p> <p>26. S + (...) + V + C: (Reflexive pronoun)</p> <p>V, S, C</p> <p>S, Reflexive pronoun</p> <p>27. S + V + O_d + O_i: (Reflexive pronounasobject)</p> <p>V, S, O_d</p> <p>Prep + O_i</p> <p>28. AFF + S + V: (Affirmative Answer)</p> <p>AFF YES</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>29. NEG + S + Aux n't: (Negative Answer)</p> <p>NEG NO</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>30. S + V + Conj + V + (...): (Coordinate Conjunction, except for temporal conjunction AND)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>Conj + 1 + 3</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>31. S + V + (...) + CONJ + S + V + (...): (Subordinate Conjunction)</p> <p>V, S, (...)</p> <p>CONJ + 1 + 3</p> <p>V, S, (...)</p> <p>(...)</p>
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<p>V, ADV</p> <p>15. S + V + ADV + Prep phrase: (PP Modification)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>Prep Phrase</p> <p>Adv, Prep Phrase</p> <p>16. ADV + S + V + (...)</p> <p>ADV</p> <p>V, S, (...)</p> <p>17. S + V + (...) + O: (Possessives)</p> <p>V, S, O</p> <p>O, Possessive</p> <p>18. S + V + Prep + (...) + O: (Approximator)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>Prep + O</p> <p>O, Approximator</p> <p>19. S + V + BOTH (...) + AND + (...): (Conjunction)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>BOTH (...) + (...)</p> <p>20. S + V + BOTH + O: (Quantifiers)</p> <p>V, S, O</p> <p>O, BOTH</p>	<p>32. CONJ + S + V + (...): (Utterance with Initial Conjunctions of Addition)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>33. CONJ + S + V + (...): (Utterances with other Initial Conjunctions)</p> <p>Conj</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>34. S + THAT/WHO/WHICH + V + (...): (Adjective clause)</p> <p>V, S, (...) [Main clause]</p> <p>CONJ + 1 + 3</p> <p>V, S, (...) [Adjective clause]</p> <p>35. S + V (+ THAT) + S + V + (...): (Noun clause)</p> <p>V, S, (THAT)</p> <p>V, S, (...)</p> <p>36. V + (...): (Parenthetical Elided Elements)</p> <p>V, (S)</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>37. S + V + (...): (Proper Nouns and Titles)</p> <p>V, S</p> <p>(...)</p>
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2.2 Analyzing the typical sentences in the units of English 6, 7, 8 and 9

2.2.1 English 6

Beginning to learn English, students are introduced to a greeting with a proposition.

The first sentence of this book has a proposition:

I am Lan. (p.11)

1. AM, I, LAN

The next sentence is of two propositions:

My name is Ba.

1. IS, NAME, BA
2. NAME, MY

At the initial level of communication, each statement has a proposition and maximally two propositions, which makes the students easily understand and acquire.

From unit 3 onwards, the propositional density increases to three and four propositions.

In unit 4, the number of propositions rises abnormally: eight propositions.

My school has four floors and my classroom is on the second floor. (p.47)

1. HAS, SCHOOL, FLOORS
2. SCHOOL, MY
3. FLOORS, FOUR
4. AND, 1, 5
5. IS, CLASSROOM, WHERE
6. WHERE= ON THE FLOOR
7. CLASSROOM, MY
8. FLOOR, SECOND

In unit 6, the highest propositional sum is only four.

Minh lives in the city with his mother, father and sister. (P. 65)

In unit 7, despite the compound sentence, the number of propositions is still four.

Similarly, in unit 12, despite the compound sentence, the highest number of propositions is still 4.

She swims, she does aerobics and she plays badminton. (p. 126)

The longest sentence in unit 14 has six propositions:

Finally, they are going to stay with their grandmother and grandfather in Ho Chi Minh City for a week. (p.142)

2.2.2 English 7

In unit 1, English 7, the majority of sentences is of one proposition, few are of two or three propositions. In particular, the most number of propositions in a sentence is six:

She is from Hue and her parents still live there. (p. 11)

Especially in unit 3, there are 10 propositions in a compound sentence constructed with many conjunctions:

It's smaller than the other two, but it's the newest of the three and it has a large, modern bathroom and a kitchen. (p. 36)

In unit 6 there is a multi-idea complex sentence, but it is composed of only seven propositions:

If they have any new stamps, they usually bring them to school. (p. 62)

A compound-complex sentence in unit 10 is of only six propositions:

I understand how you feel, but don't worry. (p. 103)

Unit 14 has a too long compound-complex sentence which is of thirteen propositions:

The older people might sleep a little and the children might play with their friends, but no one went home until the TV programs finished. (p. 142).

1. MIGHT SLEEP, THE PEOPLE
2. THE PEOPLE, OLDER
3. MIGHT SLEEP, A LITTLE
4. AND, 1, 5
5. MIGHT PLAY, THE CHILDREN
6. MIGHT PLAY, WITH FRIENDS
7. FRIENDS, THEIR
8. BUT, 4, 9
9. WENT, NO ONE, WHERE
10. WHERE = HOME
11. UNTIL 9, 12
12. FINISHED, THE PROGRAMS
13. THE PROGRAMS, TV

In unit 16, the longest compound-complex sentence is of eight propositions:

My uncle sends me postcards every time he goes away, so I have both postcards and stamps from all those cities.

2.2.3 English 8

In unit 1 there is a compound-complex sentence composed of eleven propositions:

He spends his free time doing volunteer work at a local orphanage, and he is a hard-working student who always gets good grades. (p. 13)

Unit 2 also has the longest sentence composed of eleven propositions in form of a compound sentence with a non-finite clause:

Traveling all over America, Bell demonstrated his invention to the public at countless exhibitions, and by 1877 the first telephone was in commercial use. (p. 22)

Unit 5 is of the longest compound sentence composed of seventeen propositions:

In order to remember words better, some learners even write each word and its use on a small piece of paper and stick it somewhere in their house so as to learn it at any time. (p. 49)

1. WRITE, LEARNERS WORD AND USE
2. WRITE, EVEN
3. WRITE, IN ORDER TO REMEMBER WORDS
4. REMEMBER, BETTER
5. WORD, EACH
6. USE, ITS
7. WRITE, ON PAPER
8. PAPER, A PIECE OF
9. A PIECE OF PAPER, SMALL
10. AND, 1, 11
11. STICK, (LEARNERS), IT
12. IN HOUSE
13. IN HOUSE, THEIR
14. IN THEIR HOUSE, SOMEWHERE
15. STICK, SO AS TO LEARN, IT
16. LEARN, AT TIME
17. AT TIME, ANY

The longest compound sentence in unit 6 is of ten propositions:

If possible, you can participate in other programs such as raising funds for the poor, helping street children and planting trees and flowers along the sidewalks or in the parks. (p. 58)

In unit 7 the longest compound sentence is composed of fourteen propositions:

Some of the goods in the new stores will be the same as the ones in the small shops, but the stores in the mall will offer a wider selection of products, some at cheaper prices. (p. 67)

Unit 16, the last one, consists of only ten propositions:

Finally, the water is removed from the sheets which are pressed, dried and refined until the finished paper is produced. (p. 132)

2.2.4 English 9

Unit 1 is composed of the longest complex sentence that is of twelve propositions:

Bahasa Malaysia is the primary language of instruction in all secondary schools, although some students may continue learning in Chinese or Tamil. (p. 10)

Unit 2 consists of twelve-proposition compound-complex sentence:

However, many Vietnamese women today often prefer to wear modern clothing at work, because it is more convenient. (p. 13).

In this unit there is another compound-complex sentence composed of twelve propositions.

They have added these patterns to the ao dai, so vietnamese women can continue to wear the unique dress, which is now both traditional and fashionable. (p. 14)

The longest complex sentence in unit 3 includes fifteen propositions:

People have the chance to travel between the green paddy fields and cross a small bamboo forest before they reach a big old banyan tree at the entrance to the village. (p. 23)

1. HAVE, PEOPLE, THE CHANCE
2. THE CHANCE, TO TRAVEL
3. TO TRAVEL, (BETWEEN) FIELDS
4. FIELDS, PADDY
5. PADDY, GREEN
6. TO TRAVEL, (CROSS) A FOREST
7. FOREST, BAMBOO
8. FOREST, SMALL
9. BEFORE, 1, 10
10. REACH, THEY, A TREE
11. TREE, BANYAN
12. TREE, OLD
13. TREE, BIG
14. TREE, (AT) THE ENTRANCE
15. THE ENTRANCE, (TO) THE VILLAGE

In unit 6 a long complex sentence is constructed of thirteen propositions:

When the trucks of your company have a short break on the streets around my house, the drivers have left lots of garbage on the ground after their refreshment. (p. 52)

Unit 9 is of the longest sentence consisting of nine propositions:

The word “typhoon” comes from Chinese: tai means “big” and feng means “wind”, so the word “typhoon” means “big wind”. (p. 78)

In unit 10 the longest complex sentence consists of fifteen propositions:

In 1947, Kenneth Arnold, an experienced pilot in the USA, reported that he saw nine large round objects traveling at about 2,8800 meters an hour to the left and north of Mount Rainier. (p. 83)

3 DISCUSSIONS

Having analysed the sentences in the textbooks of English 6, 7, 8 and 9, we draw out the following summary table:

Book	Unit	The most propositions in a sentence
English 6	Unit 1	2
	Unit 3	4
	Unit 4	8
	Unit 6	4
	Unit 7	4
	Unit 12	4
	Unit 14	6
English 7	Unit 1	6
	Unit 3	10
	Unit 6	7
	Unit 10	6
	Unit 14	13
	Unit 16	8
English 8	Unit 1	11
	Unit 2	11
	Unit 5	17
	Unit 6	10
	Unit 7	14
	Unit 16	10
English 9	Unit 1	12

Book	Unit	The most propositions in a sentence
	Unit 2	12
	Unit 3	15
	Unit 6	13
	Unit 9	9
	Unit 10	15

Unit 1 in English 6 is the first lesson for students learning English for 7 grades. The number of propositions in a sentence is one and only a few sentences consist of two. With this number of propositions, English students will learn easily: easily understand and remember. Unit 2 is composed of the same number of propositions. Unit 3 has the highest propositions in a sentence which is of four. This number is reasonable in comparison to the level of elementary English for 6th grade students.

Rising abnormally, unit 4 consists of eight propositions. For the students in grade 6, in the first year's learning English, this number is too much for their ability to absorb. This number creates a negative impact on students' ability to understand and remember propositions (store information).

Our proposal is to divide the sentence of these eight propositions into two sentences: the first sentence has three propositions and the second sentence has four ones. This division is logical and helps students learn and absorb more easily. The sentence is as follows:

My school has four floors.

1. HAS, SCHOOL, FLOORS
2. SCHOOL, MY
3. FLOORS, FOUR

My classroom is on the second floor.

1. IS, CLASSROOM, WHERE
2. WHERE= ON THE FLOOR
3. CLASSROOM, MY
4. FLOOR, SECOND

In units 6, 7 and 12, the highest proposition in the sentence is four. This number is consistent with the capacity of the student. The last units have the right number of propositions. Lesson 14 has six propositions. This number is not excessive and is consistent with the capacity of students near the end of the first year's studying English.

Unit 1 in English 7 has the maximum number of propositions in a sentence, six ones. In the first unit, following English 6, which corresponds to the level and capacity of the 7th graders. But Unit 4 is composed of the highest number of propositions in a sentence, ten ones. This is too high

for a student's ability to absorb. The number of propositions is reasonable in unit 6 with seven propositions and lesson 10 with six propositions, the highest in one sentence.

Unit 14 has the highest number of propositions in a spike, up to thirteen. The number of propositions is too high and unreasonable. This sentence can be cut into two sentences, one with seven propositions and one with six propositions, as follows:

The older people might sleep a little and the children might play with their friends.

1. MIGHT SLEEP, THE PEOPLE
2. THE PEOPLE, OLDER
3. MIGHT SLEEP, A LITTLE
4. AND, 1, 5
5. MIGHT PLAY, THE CHILDREN
6. MIGHT PLAY, WITH FRIENDS
7. FRIENDS, THEIR

Yet no one went home until the TV programs finished.

1. YET
2. WENT, NO ONE, WHERE
3. WHERE = HOME
4. UNTIL 9, 12
5. FINISHED, THE PROGRAMS
6. THE PROGRAMS, TV

In the remaining 2 units of English 7, the highest number of propositions in a sentence is 8 (Unit 16). This number corresponds to the ability to learn a foreign language at the end of a student's second year.

In unit 1 in English 8, the maximum number of propositions in a sentence is eleven and in the second unit the maximum number of propositions in a sentence is still eleven. This number of propositions is many, but acceptable, because students have learned English in the third year.

In unit 5, the number of propositions in a sentence spikes and reaches seventeen propositions. This excessive number will make difficulties for students to absorb. So, this sentence should split into two smaller sentences with the appropriate number of propositions for students to easily learn and remember, as follows:

In order to remember words better, some learners even write each word and its use on a small piece of paper.

1. WRITE, LEARNERS WORD AND USE

2. WRITE, EVEN
3. WRITE, IN ORDER TO REMEMBER WORDS
4. REMEMBER, BETTER
5. WORD, EACH
6. USE, ITS
7. WRITE, ON PAPER
8. PAPER, A PIECE OF
9. A PIECE OF PAPER, SMALL

Then they stick it somewhere in their house so as to learn it at any time.

1. THEN
2. STICK, THEY, IT
3. IN HOUSE
4. IN HOUSE, THEIR
5. IN THEIR HOUSE, SOMEWHERE
6. STICK, SO AS TO LEARN, IT
7. LEARN, AT TIME
8. AT TIME, ANY

The numbers of propositions in two sentences which are, in turn, nine and eight are the most appropriate for students to acquire well.

The maximum number of propositions in unit 6 which is ten is acceptable. One sentence in Unit 7 has 14 propositions, the highest number. This number of propositions is too many and needs to be separated into two short sentences as follows:

Some of the goods in the new stores will be the same as the ones in the small shops.

1. WILL BE, THE GOODS, THE SAME
2. THE GOODS, SOME OF
3. THE GOODS, (IN) THE STORES
4. THE STORES, NEW
5. THE SAME, (AS) THE ONES
6. THE ONES, (IN) THE SHOPS
7. THE SHOPS, SMALL

However, the stores in the mall will offer a wider selection of products, some at cheaper prices.

1. HOWEVER
2. WILL OFFER, THE STORES, PRODUCTS
3. THE STORES, (IN) THE MALL
4. PRODUCTS, A SELECTION OF
5. SELECTION, WIDE
6. PRODUCTS, SOME (AT) PRICES
7. PRICES CHEAPER

The maximum number of propositions in the last unit of English 8 (unit 16) is ten which is suitable for students to learn and memorize.

As a textbook at the end of junior high school, English 9 is only composed of 10 lessons and the number of propositions is relatively higher than those in the previous books. It is reasonable. Unit 1 has the highest number of propositions of twelve. The one in unit 2 is similar. The number of this proposition is high, but acceptable. In other units, like unit 9, the highest number of propositions is nine.

However, in units 3 and 10 there are sentences with the highest propositions of fifteen. The number of propositions is too high. Both sentences should be separated into sentences with the appropriate number of propositions for students to acquire better. For example, a sentence in lesson 3 should be broken down as follows:

People have the chance to travel between the green paddy fields and cross a small bamboo forest.

1. HAVE, PEOPLE, THE CHANCE
2. THE CHANCE, TO TRAVEL
3. TO TRAVEL, (BETWEEN) FIELDS
4. FIELDS, PADDY
5. PADDY, GREEN
6. TO TRAVEL, (CROSS) A FOREST
7. FOREST, BAMBOO
8. FOREST, SMALL

Then they reach a big old banyan tree at the entrance to the village.

1. REACH, THEY, A TREE
2. TREE, BANYAN
3. TREE, OLD
4. TREE, BIG
5. TREE, (AT) THE ENTRANCE

6. THE ENTRANCE, (TO) THE VILLAGE

English textbooks 6, 7, 8 and 9, in general, are good books, updating the practical knowledge between 2000 and 2010. The book is based on grammatical and vocabulary structures, graded from low to high level. The topics of the book are close to the situation of economic, social, political, etc. development of the country and the world.

In terms of propositional criteria, the sentences in this series are arranged in an increasing number of propositions. Most sentences contain a right number of propositions that are relevant to the student's cognitive and receptive level.

However, with the development of linguistics at the time, the proposition density criterion in the sentences was not applied to the compilation of this textbook series. Matching the number of propositions in the sentences is a coincidence, not a scientific one. Thus, sometimes the sentences have the proposition spikes, as follows:

Book	Unit	The most propositions in a sentence
English 6	Unit 4	8
English 7	Unit 3	10
	Unit 14	13
English 8	Unit 5	17
	Unit 7	14
English 9	Unit 3	15
	Unit 10	15

5 CONCLUSION

The proposition is one of the units that determine the number of sentences in a sentence in the most scientific and accurate way. Based on the number of propositions in a sentence, the amount of information in the sentence is determined to be less or more.

There are a number of factors that influence student's acquisition, in which the amount of information or the number of propositions plays an important role, especially in learning a foreign language. Depending on the capacity, level and stage of learning foreign languages, the number of propositions is distributed appropriately so that learners can learn the most effectively. The inappropriate proposition placement in sentences, too little or too much, will affect learner's acquisition.

The propositional formulas in this article are a synthesis from the studies of foreign scholars. The formulas help to determine the number of propositions in the sentences for convenience in sentence analysis later. However, depending on a certain language, these formulas will vary and depending on each discipline, the formulas will be adjusted appropriately.

The research suggests that when compiling textbooks, firstly English textbooks, experts should consider proposition one of the criteria for compiling sentences suitable for units and subject matters depending on the student's ability, level and academic year. With the right knowledge in the propositions, students will learn the units most effectively.

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